

Extended Colored Traveling Salesperson for Modeling Multi-Agent Mission Planning Problems

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Abstract: In recent years, multi-agent systems have been widely used in different missions, ranging from underwater to airborne. A mission typically involves a large number of agents and tasks, making it very hard for the human operator to create a good plan. A search for an optimal plan may take too long, and it is hard to make a time estimate of when the planner will finish. A Genetic algorithm based planner is proposed in order to overcome this issue. The contribution of this paper is threefold. First, an Integer Linear Programming (ILP) formulation of a novel Extensive Colored Traveling Salesperson Problem (ECTSP) is given. Second, a new objective function suitable for multi-agent mission planning problems is proposed. Finally, a reparation algorithm to allow usage of common variation operators for ECTSP has been developed.

1 Introduction

In recent years, multi-agent systems have been widely used in different missions, ranging from underwater to airborne. It can be very challenging for a human operator to devise a good plan if a mission involves a large number of agents and tasks. Given a global mission objective, resources, and constraints, the planning problem consists of assigning appropriate tasks to a set of agents in such a way that the plan is physically feasible. We assume that agents are not homogeneous: velocity and equipment may vary. Tasks have Precedence Constraints (PC) as well as equipment, or sensor requirements. Thus, the optimization problem may also include choosing the optimal set of agents for the mission. Tasks have precedence constraints (PC) as well as equipment, or sensor requirements.

This type of a combinatorial problem can be solved by an exact method or with a meta-heuristic approach. Exact methods guarantee to output optimal solution, usually by mapping a problem into a tree or a graph and searching through the nodes, pruning unfeasible branches and backtracking from dead-ends. Meta-heuristics solve problems differently, which sometimes leads to a sub-optimal solution. On the other hand, as the search space increases, exact methods fail to produce a plan within a reasonable time. In the general case, the time taken for an initial plan to be produced is less critical compared to

that of re-planning. If re-planning takes too long, the state of the system may have changed while the planning process is being done. Thus, it might be better to have a fast solution even if it is sub-optimal. The planner proposed in this work is based on GA (Holland, 1992), and has been adapted to the problem of multi-agent mission planning, described in Sect. 3.

The main contributions of this paper are to (i) give a formal problem formulation of a novel Extended Colored Traveling Salesperson Problem (ECTSP); (ii) Propose a new optimization criterion useful for multi-agent mission planning problems; and (iii) Develop a reparation algorithm to allow usage of common variation operators for ECTSP.

2 Related Work

A domain-independent taxonomy describing multi-robot task allocation (MRTA) problems has been proposed by (Gerkey and Mataric, 2004). Later, extended with temporal and ordering constraints (Nunes et al., 2017). The TSP variation that will be described in this paper can be labeled as Single-Task robots, Single-Robot tasks, Time-Extended Assignments (ST-SR-TA) with precedence constraints and heterogeneous robots.

Plans that are to be executed in a distributed fashion can nonetheless be produced by a centralized planner. A planner breaks a mission plan into smaller

pieces that are sent to the appropriate agent for execution. A multi-objective harmony search algorithm is used to solve a mission planning problem for a swarm of Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) without PCs between tasks (Landa-Torres et al., 2017). A research framework on mission planning for swarms of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) has been proposed by (Zhou et al., 2017). In general, most of the approaches used for UAV mission planning can be used in different scenarios, such as swarms of AUV in the underwater application or for swarms of terrestrial vehicles. The problem of mission planning for a swarm of UAVs can be solved using evolutionary approaches (Ramirez-Atencia et al., 2017a). The problem is modeled as a constraint satisfaction problem and solved using multi-objective GA. This work has been further extended by (Ramirez-Atencia et al., 2017b) to utilize re-planning and analysis of operator training in the control center. For a similar problem of a mission planning for cooperative UAV teams, a solution was proposed by (Bello-Ortiz et al., 2016) that uses GA to optimize a weighted linear combination of mission’s makespan and fuel consumption. This approach is further improved by (Cristian et al., 2018) by using weighted random generator strategies for the creation of new individuals. An overview of the most common optimization criteria in MRTA problems is given by (Nunes et al., 2017).

TSP expressed as an ILP was introduced by Dantzig and colleagues (Dantzig et al., 1954). Many different approaches were developed and proposed in order to solve TSP. The Lin-Kernighan approach (Keld, 2009) and GA with Edge Assembly Crossover (Yuichi and Shigenobu, 2013), are among the best performing approaches. The original problem definition of TSP is later extended to an mTSP (Bektas, 2006). An approach using sub-tours was proposed by (Giardini and Kalmár-Nagy, 2011) to solve multiple TSP (mTSP). The idea is to divide a graph into subgraphs which are solved using GA. Each subgraph represents a tour for one of the salesperson. Another extension of the original TSP is done by adding Precedence Constraint (TSPPC) (Kubo and Kasugai, 1991). mTSP and TSPPC were later combined into an mTSPPC (Zhong, 2014), although a formal problem formulation was not given. Recently, a Colored TSP formulation (CTSP) has been given by (Meng et al., 2018) in order to model and solve multiple bridge machine planning in industry.

In this paper, their approach has been further extended by the addition of PC, that is formally described as an inter-schedule dependency by (Korsah et al., 2013), multi-depots (with different source and destination depots), and heterogeneous salespersons.

Figure 1: An Illustration of the ECTSP.

3 Extended Colored TSP

Before introducing the theoretical background of the ECTSP, the connection between the theoretical model and real-world mission will be explained.

A city corresponds to a task, a salesperson to an agent¹, and a color to an equipment type (Camera, Gripper, etc.). The colors associated with an agent represent the agent’s equipment, while the colors associated with a task indicate the equipment required for its successful completion (see Fig. 1). The need for PC is apparent, as explained in this example: An agent has two tasks, e.g., scan an area for data collection, and send data back. Obviously, the data cannot be sent before it is acquired, thus the only possible ordering between the two tasks is to gather data first, and then send that data. Also, equipment heterogeneity is not the sole determinant for the differences between the agents. Every agent may have a different velocity, therefore the duration of every task depends on the selected agent.

In Fig. 1 three salespersons are shown starting from three different source depots (σ₁ to σ₃). Each of them visits a certain number of tasks and goes to the destination depot. Cities that have precedence constraints are marked with numbers (1 has to be visited before 2). Now the theoretical background of the ECTSP will be presented.

3.1 Problem Formulation

Suppose that an ECTSP has m salespersons, $s \in \mathcal{S} := \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m\}$, n cities, $v \in \mathcal{V} := \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and k colors, $c \in \mathcal{C} := \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k\}$ where $m, n, k \in \mathbb{N}$. Each salesperson s starts from a source depot σ , where $\sigma \in \Sigma := \{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_z\}$, and finishes its tour at a destination depot δ , where $\delta \in \Delta := \{\delta_1, \dots, \delta_w\}$. The superset containing all of the cities \mathcal{V} and depots is defined as $\tilde{\mathcal{V}} := \mathcal{V} \cup \{\Sigma, \Delta\}$. This problem can be formulated over a directed graph $\mathcal{G} = (\tilde{\mathcal{V}}, \mathcal{E})$, where

¹Terms *agent* and *robot* are used interchangeably throughout this work.

$\mathcal{E} : \tilde{\mathcal{V}} \times \tilde{\mathcal{V}} \mapsto \mathbb{R}_0^+$. An edge $e \in \mathcal{E}$, connecting vertices $i, j \in \tilde{\mathcal{V}}$ can be expressed as

$$e(i, j) = \begin{cases} \omega_{ij}, & \text{if } i \text{ is connected to } j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

where $\omega_{ij} \geq 0$ represents the cost of edge $e(i, j)$. The decision variable $x_{ijs} \in \{0, 1\}$ can be defined as

$$x_{ijs} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } s \text{ travels from } i \text{ to } j, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Every city $i \in \tilde{\mathcal{V}} \setminus \Delta$ has a weight $\xi(i)$, with $\xi : \tilde{\mathcal{V}} \setminus \Delta \mapsto \mathbb{R}_0^+$ (with $\xi(i) = 0$ when $i \in \Sigma$). Also, every city $i \in \mathcal{V}$ is associated with a color $f_c(i)$, with $f_c : \mathcal{V} \mapsto \mathcal{C}$. Each salesperson $s \in \mathcal{S}$ has a set of colors $\mathcal{C}_s \subseteq \mathcal{C}$ assigned to it. In contrast to city color matrix that was defined by (Li et al., 2015), here a color matrix of a salesperson s , $\mathcal{A}_s \in \{0, 1\}^{n \times n}$, shows openness of cities towards a salesperson s , and is defined as $\mathcal{A}_s := [a_{ijs}]$, with

$$a_{ijs} = \begin{cases} 1, & f_c(v_i) \in \mathcal{C}_s \wedge f_c(v_j) \in \mathcal{C}_s \wedge \pi_{ij} = 1 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

where $\Pi = [\pi_{ij}]_{n \times n}$ is the adjacency matrix indicating the precedence relations among the cities. If a certain city i needs to be visited before a city j , precedence constraints can be defined as

$$\sum_{l \in \mathcal{V}} x_{ils} \leq \sum_{k \in \tilde{\mathcal{V}} \setminus \Sigma} x_{jks}, \quad \forall s, \forall i, j \in \mathcal{V} : \pi_{ij} = 1, \pi_{ji} = 0, \quad (1)$$

and, in order to disallow a salesperson s omitting completely city j , and going directly to a destination depot from city i , a following constraint is imposed:

$$\sum_{l \in \Delta} x_{ils} \leq 0, \quad \forall s, \forall i, j \in \mathcal{V} : \pi_{ij} = 1, \pi_{ji} = 0. \quad (2)$$

The definition of the color matrix \mathcal{A}_s can be extended to include the depots as:

$$\bar{a}_{ijs} = \begin{cases} a_{ijs}, & i, j \in \mathcal{V}, \\ 1, & (i \in \Sigma, j \in \tilde{\mathcal{V}} \setminus \Sigma) \vee (i \in \tilde{\mathcal{V}} \setminus \Delta, j \in \Delta), \\ 0, & (i, j \in \Sigma) \vee (i, j \in \Delta). \end{cases}$$

A salesperson s is allowed to only visit the cities specified in its extended color matrix $\bar{\mathcal{A}}_s$:

$$x_{ijs} \leq \bar{a}_{ijs}, \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \forall i \in \tilde{\mathcal{V}} \setminus \Delta, \forall j \in \tilde{\mathcal{V}} \setminus \Sigma, i \neq j. \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, a salesperson s must enter (Eq. 4) and leave (Eq. 5) each city exactly once.

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{i \in \tilde{\mathcal{V}} \setminus \Delta} x_{ijs} = 1, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{V}, i \neq j \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{j \in \tilde{\mathcal{V}} \setminus \Sigma} x_{ijs} = 1, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, i \neq j. \quad (5)$$

The final destination of a salesperson s is always a destination depot δ :

$$\sum_{i \in \tilde{\mathcal{V}} \setminus \Delta} \sum_{j \in \Delta} x_{ijs} = 1, \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}. \quad (6)$$

It is important to note that it is allowed for some salespersons to go directly from a source depot σ to a destination depot δ , i.e., $x_{ijs} = 1, i \in \Sigma, j \in \Delta$.

The starting location of a salesperson s is always a source depot σ :

$$\sum_{i \in \Sigma} \sum_{j \in \tilde{\mathcal{V}} \setminus \Sigma} x_{ijs} = 1, \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}. \quad (7)$$

The number of salespersons \mathcal{B}_σ in each source depot σ is given, and it is such that $\sum_{i \in \Sigma} \mathcal{B}_i = |\mathcal{S}|$, and:

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{j \in \tilde{\mathcal{V}} \setminus \Sigma} x_{ijs} = \mathcal{B}_i, \quad \forall i \in \Sigma. \quad (8)$$

To eliminate the sub-tours, it is required that for each nonempty subset $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, the number of edges between the nodes of \mathcal{M} must be at most $|\mathcal{M}| - 1$:

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{M}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{M}} x_{ijs} \leq |\mathcal{M}| - 1, \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \forall \mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{M} \neq \emptyset. \quad (9)$$

A salesperson s cannot travel from a city i to the same city i :

$$x_{iis} = 0, \quad \forall i \in \tilde{\mathcal{V}}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}. \quad (10)$$

3.2 Objective Function

In multi-agent systems a mission can involve an optimization of many different parameters. Commonly, mission duration is minimized, however a duration of a mission can be defined in various ways. (Maoudj et al., 2015) defined mission duration as the sum of all tasks in a mission (minSUM), where (Bello-Organ et al., 2016) describe mission duration as the time interval from the start time of the first task to the end time of the last task (minMAX). Neither of these approaches is suitable for the problem presented in this paper. The former approach can produce a plan where one agent is doing much more work than the other agents. In an actual AUV mission, this can mean that the extraction vessels and the crew have to stay in the open sea much longer increasing the overall cost of the mission. The latter approach minimizes the maximum cost of an agent over all the agents. This approach works well if tasks are instantaneous or have the same duration. However, if there is a task that dominates the duration of the other tasks², then the

²Its duration is larger than the makespan of any other agent's plan

mission would not be optimized at all. This issue is partly mitigated in the work of (Alighanbari et al., 2003) where a linear aggregation function is used to minimize the maximum and average task completion times, as well as total idle times. This approach favors the usage of as many agents as possible, and it might lead to an increased cost, if agent needs to be deployed to the environment. In order to avoid aforementioned problems, a weighted combination of *min-MAX*

$$f_m = \min_x \max_s \sum_{i \in \mathcal{T} \setminus \Delta} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{T} \setminus \Sigma} (\omega_{ij} + \xi(i)) x_{ijs}$$

and *minSUM*

$$f_s = \min_x \sum_{i \in \mathcal{T} \setminus \Delta} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{T} \setminus \Sigma} (\omega_{ij} + \xi(i)) x_{ijs}, \quad \forall s$$

is proposed as objective function:

$$J = w_1 f_m + w_2 f_s \quad (11)$$

subject to constraints from (1) to (10), where $w_1, w_2 > 0$ are user defined weights.

4 Genetic Mission Planner (GMP)

In addition to TSP, GA and its numerous variations have been widely used to solve other combinatorial optimization problems like Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) (Baker and Ayechev, 2003), Job Shop Scheduling problems (Nisha and Nathi Ram, 2015), as well as Resource Constrained problems (Brie and Morignot, 2005). Although the initial plan making is not bounded by time, the re-planning is. Re-planning, in this case, can be seen as planning again with new initial conditions. Since multi-agent missions are usually costly and autonomy of agents is limited as well, the re-planning process should be very fast. This is one of the reasons for the use of a metaheuristic approach over exact methods.

Chromosome encoding is done in the same way as it done by (Miloradović et al., 2017), thus two arrays of integers, representing the genes, are used. The first array consists of integers representing tasks and agents, whereas the second array represents task parameters (PC, equipment requirements, duration of the task, and location) as shown in the Fig. 2. Chromosome length can be fixed *a priori* if the length of a

A1	T3	T5	T2	A2	T7	T7	T4			
0	P1	P0	P1	0	P1	P2	P1	0	0	0
	Agent		Task			Parameter			Inactive	

Figure 2: An example of an individual in the population.

plan (number of tasks + number of agents involved) is known. However, if a planner can introduce a new task or optimize the number of agents (some agents might not be used even if they are available for a mission) then a variable chromosome length is preferred. In this paper a mix of these two approaches is used - chromosome length is fixed, in addition, besides active genes (AG), a certain number of inactive genes is introduced. The reason for this is that although the number of tasks in a mission is fixed, the planner is allowed to optimize the number of agents involved. This implies that the number of AG is $n + 1 \leq AG \leq n + m$ thus the chromosome length is fixed to the size of $n + m$.

The initial population is created at random with the respect to given constraints. As a start, the minimum number of agents and agent types (with appropriate equipment) are determined. Then a number of agents in the chromosome is randomly picked in the range of the bare minimum and the maximum number of available agents. For example, if all agents have the same equipment, then the number of agents in a chromosome would be in a range of 1 to m . After this step, a list of possible tasks for every agent is created. The number of tasks per agent is randomly determined based on the previously created list. Two or more agents may have the ability to do the same task, e.g., a task requires a sonar, and there are three agents with sonar available. In this specific case, a task is randomly assigned to one of the valid agents. Task assignment is repeated until there are no more tasks left to assign and the whole process is repeated for every individual in the population.

4.1 Precedence Reparation Algorithm

In a classical implementation of a GA for TSP, chromosomes are arrays consisting of genes (city identifiers). In this case, crossover operators can mix individuals in many possible ways and produce feasible solutions. The only thing that has to be taken into account is to disallow city duplicates in a potential solution. In contrast to the TSP, implementation of the crossover operators for ECTSP is not trivial, since there are PCs that need to be taken into account, in order to avoid the creation of infeasible solutions.

Since variation operators (crossover and mutation) do not have the ability to preserve or guarantee to create offspring with a valid ordering, a Precedence Constraint Reparation (PCR) operator has been developed. The PCR is applied after the creation of the initial population, crossover (when used), and mutation operator.

The algorithm starts by iterating through each task

gene of each individual. When a task gene with incorrect PC is found, the algorithm searches for the other inter-related task. Two cases can be distinguished. In the first case (case 1) both tasks are allocated to the same agent, while in the second case (case 2) both tasks are not allocated to the same agent.

In case (1) task genes are simply swapped. In case (2) there are three different sub-cases. In sub-case (1) both tasks are allocated to agents able to handle defined constraints, then a uniform random mechanism is used to determine which of the tasks will be re-allocated and which one will retain the previous allocation. In sub-case (2) one of the tasks is allocated to an agent that cannot fulfill task's constraints. In that case, the invalid task is allocated to the agent of the task with valid constraints. In sub-case (3) both of the tasks are allocated to agents that cannot fulfill their constraints. In this case, a search is performed to find if there is an agent available that can fulfill both of the tasks. If that agent exists, both tasks are re-allocated to that agent. In every case, the location of the re-allocated task within an agent is randomly determined with respect to the PC. An example of aforementioned

cases is given in Fig. 3. Let's assume that task T8 has to be done after task T5. Only agents A1 and A4 have the necessary equipment to fulfill these tasks. In case (1) both tasks are allocated to the proper agent (A1) and simple task swap is done. The first sub-case of case(2) shows the problem when each task is allocated to a different agent, however, both the A1 and A4 are able to fulfill the allocated task. Options here are to move either T8 to A1 after T5 or T7, or to move T5 to A4 before T8. In Fig. 3 the latter option is shown. In the sub-case (2) of case (2) T8 is allocated to A2 and A2 does not meet the requirements of T8. The solution is to move T8 to A1, either after T5 or T7. In Fig. 3 the latter option is shown. The last sub-case of case (2) shows a problem when both of the tasks are allocated to the agents that do not meet the tasks' requirements. In this case, first the pre-Task (task T5) is re-allocated to A1. T5 can be allocated to any position in the A1's plan. In Fig. 3 the 1st position is chosen, right after gene A1. After this is done T8 is re-allocated to A1. Possible options are after T5, T2, T1 or T7. In Fig. 3 T8 is shown to be re-allocated after T2. As already mentioned, when making a decision of where to re-allocate certain task a uniform random function is used.

Figure 3: An example of the mechanism of PCR, showing both cases and all three possible sub-cases of case (2).

4.2 Mutation

Mutation is the source of variability as it allows genetic diversity in the population. Every individual has a low probability to be selected for mutation. In this paper, two types of mutation schemes are introduced. One operates on the task genes through swapping tasks and inserting new genes (Alg. 1), whereas the other mutates agent genes through growing (adding agents) and shrinking (removing agents) from the chromosome as shown in (Alg. 2).

Task swap mutation swaps two task genes in a chromosome, meaning that it can both swap tasks

Algorithm 1 Task Swap/Insert Mutation

- 1: **procedure** TASKMUTATION(*population*)
- 2: Select random chromosome *i* from the pop.
- 3: Select random task gene from *i*
- 4: **case (1)** - Task Swapping
- 5: Create a list of valid tasks for swapping
- 6: Choose a task gene randomly from that list
- 7: Swap tasks
- 8: **case (2)** - Task Insertion
- 9: Create a list of suitable agents for chosen task
- 10: Randomly select agent and position and insert gene from step 3.
- 11: **return** modified chromosome

Algorithm 2 Agent Growth/Shrink Mutation

```
1: procedure AGENTMUTATION(population)
2:   Select random chromosome i from the pop.
3:   case (1) - Agent Growth
4:     If there are available agents
5:       Select random position to insert new agent
6:       Validate that no constraint is violated
7:       Add new agent
8:       Check if new agent's plan is valid
9:       If not, reassign invalid tasks to other agents
10:  case (2) - Agent Shrink
11:    If the minimum is not reached
12:      Select random agent gene for removal
13:      Remove that gene
14:      Reassign its tasks to other agents with the
        respect to constraints
15:  return modified chromosome
```

within a single agent or between two agents. Insert mutation chooses a task and inserts it in a new location in a chromosome, same as in previously explained mutation, the insertion can be within the same agent or different one.

Agent shrink mutation removes one agent from a chromosome, reassigning its tasks to other agents if possible (Alg. 2). If such action would cause an invalid plan the action is skipped. For example, removing the only agent from a plan or removing the only agent with the required equipment for a specific task. Growth agent mutation adds a new agent to the plan if the limit of available agents is not reached in that specific chromosome. The new agent gene is randomly inserted, acquiring tasks from that location in the chromosome up to the next agent gene or end of the chromosome. If there are conflicting (a task not supported by assigned agent) tasks, they are randomly reassigned to other agents. Both algorithms take into account color constraints ensuring that the mutation process does not produce infeasible solutions.

4.3 Fitness Function

The fitness function evaluates the individuals, in the population, by calculating a quantitative measure, i.e., fitness or cost. Depending on the design of the GA and its operators, population might consist of both feasible and infeasible or only feasible solutions.

In the first case, where operators are not bound to always produce valid chromosomes, the fitness function has a penalty/award system in order to deal with invalid chromosomes (Miloradović et al., 2016). The second approach, used in this paper, is to define variation operators in such a way only feasible solutions

can be produced. The former approach has the advantage of variation operators being simpler to implement, whereas in the latter approach the search space is reduced.

In the fitness function, the candidate solution that is being evaluated is first divided into agent's plans, i.e., sub-plans per each agent. Each plan is evaluated separately and results are combined afterward to form an overall chromosome fitness. The objective function that is being minimized is given in Eq. (11).

5 Simulation Results

The proposed approach is tested in the use case of underwater mission planning (SWARMS³ project). In order to ease the process of a mission preparation, a special Mission Management Tool (MMT) is developed. This tool allows a human operator an intuitive way of creating complex missions involving different types of robots with non-overlapping abilities, e.g., due to different sensory modalities, and configurations, as well as tasks. When the operator has prepared the mission, it is translated into a formal model (see Sect. 3) which is forwarded to the GMP (see Sect. 4). After this step, the result is presented to the operator on the map and with a Gantt chart.

The experimental platform was i5-7200U @ 2.4GHz CPU with 8GB of DDR4 RAM. The GMP is implemented in the C++ programming language. Four different underwater scenarios are used for evaluating the proposed planning algorithm. Tasks can have 3 different equipment requirements (colors) (Camera, Sonar, and Salinity). All AUVs are heterogeneous. Each of the scenarios has a certain number of precedence constraints that need to be fulfilled. The objective function (Eq. 11) is used with W_1 and W_2 being 1 and 0.1, respectively. Complete scenario settings are presented in Table 1. Due to the paper length limitations, GA parameters will be given without giving simulation results. A number of generation was set to 5000, with a population consisting of 200 individuals. Crossover probability was 65%, mutation probability was 10%, and elitism 20%. Three types of crossover operator were tested—One Point, Partially Mapped (PM), and Edge Recombination. Since results showed no statistically significant difference between them, all simulations including crossover operator were done with the PM crossover.

Results of the planning process are shown in Table 2 for 4 different variation operator's settings. All scenarios had 1 starting depot for all the vehicles, while

³<http://swarms.eu>

Table 1: Settings for different simulation scenarios

Sim.	Task's settings					AUV's settings			
	Camera	Sonar	Salinity	#PC	#	Camera	Sonar	Salinity	#
1	4	3	3	3	10	AUV 2	AUV 1	AUV 1,2	2
2	7	6	6	5	19	AUV 2,3	AUV 1,3	AUV 1,2	3
3	17	16	16	10	49	AUV 2,3,4,5	AUV 1,3,4	AUV 1,2,4	5
4	33	27	40	14	100	AUV 2,3,4,5	AUV 1,3,4,6	AUV 1,2,4,7	7

*(Sim. - Simulation scenario; #PC - Number of precedence constraints; # - Total number of tasks (or AUVs) in a scenario)

Table 2: Simulation results for 4 different scenarios

Sim.	Different Variation Operators Settings											
	Mutation			Mut. & PC			X & Mut.			X, Mut. & PC		
	mdn.	std.	best	mdn.	std.	best	mdn.	std.	best	mdn.	std.	best
1	3041	0	3041	3041	0	3041	3041	0	3041	3041	0	3041
2	4231	278	4047	4047	37	4047	4202	252	4047	4047	41	4047
3	7793	$1.4 \cdot 10^5$	6102	5871	280	5490	7761	$1.7 \cdot 10^5$	6063	5956	252	5506
4	13795	$3.1 \cdot 10^5$	10961	10738	550	9378	13331	$2.8 \cdot 10^5$	10895	10797	594	9612

*(Mut. - Mutation; X - Crossover, PC - Precedence Constraint Reparation; mdn. - median; std. - standard deviation; best - best solution found)

Table 3: Statistical tests of the gathered results from 4 different simulations using different variation operators settings

Mut. & PC vs.	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4	Critical value
	p - value	p - value	p - value	p - value	
Mutation	1	$6.76 \cdot 10^{-26}$	$8.77 \cdot 10^{-33}$	$3.62 \cdot 10^{-33}$	0.0033
X & Mut.	1	$2.03 \cdot 10^{-26}$	$8.99 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$5.50 \cdot 10^{-32}$	0.0067
X, Mut. & PC	1	0.0034	0.2350	0.2350	0.0100

scenario 1 had 2 exit depots and each next scenario had plus one exit depot, making it finally to 5 exit depots in scenario 4. For every scenario, the algorithm was run 100 times.

A series of statistical tests were conducted to see if the **null hypothesis**: "Using different variation operator settings makes no difference on the final result" is true. It is assumed that the samples used in these experiments are random and independent.

Since the sample data can be highly skewed and have extended tails, an average of that data can produce a value that behaves non-intuitively, thus median was used instead of the mean. This means that the non-parametric Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon test is used. Since multiple comparisons are performed, Benjamini-Hochberg (B-H) procedure is applied in order to adjust the false discovery rate. The B-H critical value is calculated as $(i/m) \cdot Q$, where i is the rank, m number of tests and Q false discovery rate set to 0.01. The variation operator settings that had the best median value is compared to all other setups in all 4 scenarios. Since there is a statistically significant difference between the results (Table 3), the null hypothesis is rejected.

Results show that in every scenario, a mutation with PC reparation algorithm produces equally good or better results than other setups. From scenario 3

and 4, it can be concluded that a crossover operator is not needed since it doesn't help to improve the final result. Moreover, in scenario 2, the use of crossover leads to worse results than in the setup without it. Scenario 1 is solved equally good with all tested variation operators settings.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, the mission planning problem is modeled as a novel variation of TSP, referred to as Extended Colored TSP. The problem formulation was given in a form of an ILP problem in Sect. 3. It is concluded that ECTSP can be applied to model different real-world problems in addition to being relevant from a theoretical point of view. In this work, GA is adapted to be used for ECTSP's objective function optimization with a few improvements in variation operators in order to handle given constraints. As demonstrated, the objective function presented in this work is more suitable for the intended mission planning domain than other specific solutions found in the literature. In addition, a precedence constraint reparation algorithm is presented. This algorithm makes the use of crossover operator unnecessary, thus saving valuable computation time, which is of major impor-

tance in the context of the population-based search. Presented results show the usefulness of using GMP for solving ECTSP.

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